

DigiVet - Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

WP2 - Deliverable 2.2

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Introduction

The DigiVet project – “Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health”, funded by NordForsk, is a three-year project running between 2021 – 2023, involving the countries UK, Denmark, Sweden, Norway and Estonia. DigiVet is composed of three work packages (WP), where the first, WP1, will investigate the current opportunities, investments, and challenges regarding digitalisation of livestock data. This report is a deliverable of WP2, and WP2 is dedicated to **Creating Smarter Data Systems** and focuses on practical implementations to improve data use and digitalisation. The last part, WP3, will assess broader societal and end-user perspectives regarding the solutions developed in WP2.

The project will also use three different case studies (CS), each of them performed through all WPs. CS1 is about food safety, with particular emphasis on *Salmonella Dublin* in Denmark, CS2 is about health security with focus on antimicrobial use (AMU) mainly in Sweden and Norway, and CS3 concerns economic security focusing on transboundary spread of African swine fever (ASF), involving all the countries participating in DigiVet. More information about the project and other tasks and deliverables can be found on the DigiVet community on Zenodo¹.

In deliverable 1.1² in WP1 and the first part of deliverable 2.1³ in WP2 we investigated currently available data sources and data ecosystems, and associated regulatory frameworks, in the different countries for each of the case studies. In the report from deliverable 2.1⁴ in WP2 we also explored more challenges with the current data and workflows, partly from a perspective of the FAIR-principles⁵ (about findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable data). Some of the results from those deliverables were:

- The purpose of using some data sources might have changed over time, so data quality and content might not be optimal for current use cases.
- Data sharing between different organisations within a country or between countries is often limited due to legal barriers and confidentiality issues.
- Some data (or metadata and documentation of datasets) are not findable or accessible. Even in some cases where data is shared, the accessibility is not good. For example, due to limited technical solutions, information losses along the transitions or due to bad documentation.
- In some cases, similar datasets exist in many countries (for example due to common legislation) – but there are still differences in data quality, content and structure which limits the interoperability between countries and also between datasets.
- The challenges mentioned about findability, accessibility and interoperability reduce the opportunities to reuse data and workflows.

Based on the results from previous deliverables we will in this deliverable suggest workflows to enhance digitalisation and support decision-making. This report will focus on mapping and/or documenting the content of the available datasets to gain a better understanding of the data and how we can work with it in latter tasks, and to improve findability and accessibility of the data by documenting metadata. We will also suggest some common data structures (with better findability and accessibility through publishing it on Zenodo) that existing data could be processed into to

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/digivet/>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/7462364#.Y7V6xnbMKMo>

³ https://zenodo.org/record/6322649#.Y7V_8nbMKHs

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/record/6393053#.Y7WALHbMKHs>

⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

enhance interoperability. Based on the common data structures, we can develop solutions (in later tasks and deliverables) that are reusable for various countries. However, the needs and circumstances for each case study are different, therefore this deliverable is divided into three different chapters, one for each case study.

The broader aim of this deliverable is to improve digitalisation and overcome some of the challenges identified in the previous deliverables.

Common note

Note that the documentation of the contents of the datasets have been acquired in different ways. For some case studies and countries, direct access to the databases or through other interfaces building on the databases are provided. In other cases, documentation from the databases, or documentation regarding exported datasets from the databases, have been acquired. Some datasets are sent between organisations and some information might be lost during the way. This means that some existing variables may not be included in this deliverable, variable names may not be the same as in the original databases and valid values and format of some variables might also differ from original data sources.

Case study 1 – Food safety, *Salmonella* Dublin

CS1 - BACKGROUND

Food safety is a very diverse topic, and depending on the pathogen under consideration may involve data from a wide variety of data sources including animal-level data (e.g. milk or serum test results), farm-level data (e.g. bulk-tank test results, farm biosecurity and location), animal movement data, abattoir observations, and potentially food chain data to capture potential sources of contamination during processing and packaging. For the specific case of *Salmonella* Dublin in cattle, the most relevant data are animal-level test results, farm-level data, and cattle movement data. Of these, cattle movement and farm locations are the only data type that is recorded consistently among the countries considered within this project. *Salmonella* Dublin test data are recorded both at animal level and farm level in Sweden and Denmark, although these are considered to be highly sensitive data in both countries due to the perceived potential for misuse of the data should these be made openly available – these topics were explored thoroughly within WP1. Current farm-level farm classifications for *Salmonella* Dublin are made publicly available for Denmark via a public web interface at <http://chr.fvst.dk> – however no API (application programming interface) is provided, so this interface is of practical use only for collecting information on a small number of specific farms (this is useful for farmers when making decisions on who to trade with, for example). The UK has no active surveillance system currently in place for *Salmonella* Dublin, so no test data are routinely collected, and the data collected as part of the passive surveillance programme is not made available at farm or animal level.

As part of this project, we were able to obtain animal-level and farm-level data for *Salmonella* Dublin in Denmark, which was used to generate the dashboard application that is provided as a deliverable from WP2. However, due to the relative simplicity of the data format combined with the extreme sensitivity of these data (and therefore the legal difficulty in making the findings and/or relatively simple data pipelines public), the focus of this CS shifted towards developing technical solutions to safe sharing and storage of sensitive data such as animal- and farm-level test results for *Salmonella* Dublin.

CS1 - COMMON DATA STRUCTURES

Two different data structures were considered for this CS, as outlined below:

Cattle movement data

Common legislation requires all movements of cattle to be registered, and underlying data are held in a similar format for each of the countries involved in this project. These data are not made publicly available, although access to processed datasets is typically granted by the relevant national authorities in relation to relevant consultancy tasks and research projects, such as DigiVet. Depending on the country, these take one of two forms:

1. “Raw” data, where each in- and out-movement is recorded separately, following the mechanism by which the data are reported by the livestock industry. The precise naming of the columns depends on the country, but conceptually each row reflects either an “incoming” or “outgoing” activity relating to a given animal ID and farm ID on a specified date, with the type of activity (including birth, death, movement, slaughter, and post-slaughter carcass movement) also recorded.
2. “Processed” data, whereby the raw data has been pre-processed so that the matching “outgoing” and “incoming” movements have been combined into a single record (following potential corrections for mis-recording in the data), and potentially birth/death/slaughter etc records have been removed. Again, the precise naming of the columns depends on the

country, but the core information is “AnimalID”, “OriginFarmID”, “DestinationFarmID”, “Date”, and potentially other information such as activity type if birth/death records are retained in the data.

This data is very similar conceptually to the pig movement data considered in more detail in CS3.

Salmonella Dublin test data

In Denmark, an active surveillance and control/eradication programme is in place for *Salmonella* Dublin, within which all animal-level and farm-level test results for the presence of antibodies in blood and/or milk are recorded at national level, and used to generate the farm-level classifications displayed at <http://chr.fvst.dk>. The underlying data is considered highly sensitive, and is not typically made available to anybody outside of the organisation that holds the data (SEGES). Similar data are also collected in Sweden, with the same constraints on usage and distribution. The Danish data were made available for this project, although with strong constraints on distribution of the data that preclude a detailed description being included in this report. However, the underlying data structure is relatively simple, consisting primarily of the test type and result, date, and animal identification numbers (or farm identification numbers for bulk tank milk results). We expect that the equivalent data is stored in similar formats in Sweden.

CS1 – GOLDENEYE WORKFLOW

The primary challenge within this CS was handling the *Salmonella* Dublin test data, which were considered to be extremely sensitive by the data owner. We therefore developed and implemented the Goldeneye sOLution for moDErN data safEtY procEdures (goldeneye⁶), which is an encryption-based workflow that allows these data to be safely shared between SEGES and specifically named individuals within the Danish project partner. Because we recognised that this problem is far from unique, we designed goldeneye to be sufficiently generic to work with any dataset, and to include the possibility of remotely controlled access authorisation that can be revoked by the data owner either at a pre-planned time point (e.g. the planned end date of the project) and/or in response to a suspected security breach within the organisation of the data recipient.

The goldeneye workflow uses a hybrid strategy of symmetric and asymmetric encryption, which are implemented using the open-source sodium cryptography library (<https://doc.libsodium.org>). Sharing multiple dataset within a project can be done by setting up a data-sharing group for that project, which further enhances security by tightly controlling the pool of users to which access *may* be given for a specific dataset. The conceptual procedure is as follows:

- Alec and Boris want to share data, so they set up a new data-sharing group called “Janus” using the goldeneye package in R.
- After setup, each user has a public-private keypair for use with asymmetric encryption.
- Their public key is made available online so that all “Janus” users can download the key corresponding to each user.
- Alec can then encrypt data for Boris using goldeneye, which:
 - Encrypts the data using a randomly generated 256-bit symmetric encryption key for efficient and robust encryption.
 - Encrypts the symmetric key separately for Boris and Alec using each of their public keys.
 - Bundles the encrypted data and encrypted symmetric keys together as a goldeneye encrypted file.

⁶ <https://www.costmodds.org/goldeneye>; <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Backronym>; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Recursive_acronym

- Alec can safely store this file and/or send this file to Boris over insecure channels: it can only be decrypted using Boris's (or Alec's) private key

More details and user instructions on this workflow are included in the goldeneye package vignette, which is provided as an appendix to this deliverable and can also be accessed from inside the goldeneye tool itself, as documented within deliverable 2.3

CS1 – NEXT STEPS

The activities under case study 1 for the remainder of the project will be split into two streams:

1. Work specific to *Salmonella* Dublin, including further analysis of the Danish data to understand the implications of the surveillance system used in Denmark, and work on a user-friendly tool for stakeholders to help them understand the likely overall performance of the surveillance system and sensitivity to potentially unknown parameters such as diagnostic test performance.
2. Work generic to best-practice procedures for working with sensitive data, focussing primarily on further development of the goldeneye workflow.

Case study 2 – Antimicrobial use

CS2 - BACKGROUND

How AMU is, or should be calculated, vary between the countries, depending on how antimicrobials are sold and used, legislation, and available data sources. A common reproducible workflow to create FAIR AMU-data might therefore not be plausible or relevant. Norway and Denmark already have experience with calculating the AMU, whereas Sweden have not worked with this systematically before (only antimicrobial sales). Therefore, this case study is mainly conducted with a Swedish perspective, with input from Norwegian and Danish representatives in DigiVet.

Data on antimicrobials used by veterinarians in Sweden has historically had poor quality and it has therefore been hard to make realistic estimates or calculations of AMU. However, recent legislation in EU (article 57 of Regulation 2019/6) implies that the member states will be required to report AMU to EU, and this has in Sweden led to the development of a new system to collect data on AMU. This system was not yet in place when this task was initiated.

In this task we therefore investigated the planned data structure for the new system to collect Swedish data on AMU, and had discussions with Norway and Denmark about available data in the different countries. Based on this, the main focus was to suggest and document a common data structure (with improved FAIR-ness) that could be useful for further analysis that can be derived from existing data sources in the different countries. Instead of creating a conceptual diagram of the knowledge graph, we specified and documented metadata and content of the common data structure in an excel sheet (“D2.2 – CS2 AMU – Content mapping and common data structure.xlsx”, attached to this report). This was assessed to be more relevant and of better use, to understand what workflow might be needed to structure and translate source data into this format, and how to create tools based on this common data structure.

There are already defined data formats to report AMU to EMA⁷ (according to European legislation). The common data structure in this case study is inspired by the data format, but adapted to also include other information to use in analyses and in the dashboard to be developed. We also used results from stakeholder workshops (in WP1 of DigiVet), and discussions between Swedish, Norwegian, and Danish representants in the DigiVet team, to create the suggested common data structure. The structure was further updated to incorporate some of the feedback that were given at another stakeholder workshop (in WP3 of DigiVet) where the dashboard (D2.4) was presented.

The processes or workflows to format source data into the common data structure will probably, as already mentioned, differ between the countries and may also require different data sources combined, which is why no generic workflow was developed within this case study. However, we have looked at Norwegian and Danish processes that are already used to calculate AMU from their available data sources, to discuss if something similar might be used in Sweden when the new system for collecting AMU-data is in place. The need to use the common data structure and the tools developed in WP2 may also vary a lot for different countries (depending on already existing workflows and tools), but we hope that the results of this report and other deliverables in DigiVet can be of use to other countries outside of DigiVet to enhance digitalisation of AMU-data.

CS2 - COMMON DATA STRUCTURE AND CONTENT DOCUMENTATION AND MAPPING

⁷ <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/veterinary-regulatory/overview/antimicrobial-resistance/european-surveillance-veterinary-antimicrobial-consumption-esvac#interactive-esvac-database-section>

The suggested common data structure is explained in detail in the excel sheet, “D2.2 – CS2 AMU – Content mapping and common data structure.xlsx”, attached to this deliverable, and an overview of the data structure is shown in Table 1. The main content of this dataset is the amount of different medical products and active ingredients (of antimicrobials) that have been used in animals. The use of antimicrobials can be derived from different data sources, for example pharmacy sales, veterinary journal records, or use by feed mills. The purpose of the common data structure is that various countries could process and structure data from different sources into this format to then be able to use solutions developed in later deliverables in WP2, and possibly compare AMU between countries. The common data structure for example suggests including time of use and geographical information, information about the treated animals such as production type, gender and age, and also information on indication or diagnosis, purpose of treatment, etc. Some suggested information may not be available in all countries, but the goal should be to include as much information as possible.

Table 1 - Overview of the suggested common data structure in case study 2 on antimicrobial use. The full documentation is given in the excel “D2.2 – CS2 AMU – Content mapping and common data structure.xlsx”, attached to this deliverable.

category	variable	explanation
Entry	EntryID	Unique identifier of the entry
	TypeOfDataSource	Type of entry in database, for example if it is a pharmacy sale or journal record
	IncludeAsUse	States if the entry should be included in calculations of AMU
Date	DateTransaction	Date of sale transaction (if the entry is a sale)
	DateTreatment	Date of treatment
	DateOther	Other available date
	DateOtherComment	Comment to explain DateOther
Geographical information	Country	2-letter country code (ISO 3166-1 alpha-2)
	NUTS2	Level 2 of nomenclature of territorial units for statistics classification, from European Union
	NUTS3	Level 3 of nomenclature of territorial units for statistics classification, from European Union
	GeoComment	Comment to explain what geographic location is specified (e.g. location of the pharmacy or treated herd)
Animal information	HerdID	Identification of herd, if applicable.
	AnimalSpecies	Animal species
	AnimalType	Type of animal production (if relevant)
	ProductionType	Type of production
	Gender	Gender of the treated animal/s
	AgeCategory	Age category of treated animal/s
Treatment and medication information	TreatmentPurpose	Purpose of the treatment.
	Indication	Indication, symptom or medical condition that was the reason for treatment.
	Diagnosis	Diagnosis, free text at the moment
	AdministrationMethod	Administration method of medical product
	TreatedUnit	Information on whether the entry reports treatment to an individual or group of animals
	NumberOfAnimals	Number of treated animals
	MedicalProductName	Name of the medical product
	MedicalProductCode	Code identifying medical product
	ATCcode	The ATC (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical) code of the medical product
	ActiveIngredient	Name of active ingredient
ActiveSubstanceKg	Amount of active substance, given in kg	

Two main data sources have been identified as necessary to calculate AMU in Sweden. These are the pharmacy sales (FOTA) and veterinary records of medical use (Vet@data). The latter will be collected through the new system mentioned earlier. More information about these data sources and legislation can be found in deliverables 1.1 – “Mapping data ecosystems and associated regulatory frameworks”, 2.1 – “Data Collection, Curation, Preservation” and 1.3 – “Stakeholder workshop reports” from the DigiVet project, found at the DigiVet Zenodo community⁸. However,

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/communities/digivet/>

to better understand the data sources and to enhance FAIR-ness (focusing on Sweden), the attached excel also include metadata on the two Swedish data sources mentioned. Due to confidentiality issues and the fact that the new system for veterinary records was not yet in place when the task was initiated (and still under construction to be improved when the task was performed), no real Swedish data was retrieved for this case study. Hence, the metadata documentation in the attachment “D2.2 – CS2 AMU – Content mapping and common data structure.xlsx”, is summarised from information and documentation retrieved from stakeholders working with the data, or from preliminary database documentation.

Many variables in FOTA and Vet@data can then be mapped into the common data structure, for example information on date, geographical location, animal species, purpose of treatment and information about the medical product and amount of the product or active ingredient sold or used (in some cases more information about the medical products would need to be fetched from separate medical product registers). However, more steps will be needed to convert data into the common structure and estimate the actual use (it will not be enough to just map the content and add the data sources together), which will need testing and validation with real data. The workflow to do this is discussed more in the next section.

CS2 - WORKFLOW

Norway and Denmark already have processes in place to estimate AMU based on available sources. Figure 1 and Figure 2 show sketches of the Norwegian workflow to calculate AMU based on VetReg (the Norwegian database for veterinary prescriptions and veterinary use of medicines) and the register with information on medical products (SLV). Figure 3 show different data sources that are combined into VetStat (the Danish veterinary prescription database). VetStat contains data on estimated AMU and there are already tools to analyse and visualise the AMU in Denmark. To process the Norwegian and Danish data into the common data structure would require some additional steps, where available information is mapped or translated to fit the common data structure. This may not be seen as useful however, as Norway and Denmark already have some tools to monitor AMU, and depends on if there is an additional need for the tools developed later in WP2. This might be discussed further in stakeholder workshops in WP3 of DigiVet.

Prepare AMU raw data

Figure 1 – Sketch of process in Norway to combine data sources into raw data on antimicrobial use (AMU). VetReg is the Norwegian Food Safety Authority’s database for veterinary prescriptions and veterinary use of

medicines and NOMA (Norwegian Medicine Agency) medicine register contains information on medical products.

Calculate AMU

Figure 2 - Sketch of process in Norway to calculate amount of used antimicrobials (AM) based on raw data.

Figure 3 - Sketch of process in Denmark to combine different data sources into VetStat (the Danish veterinary prescription database) that hold information on antimicrobial use (AMU). Denmark already have tools to analyse and visualise the AMU, as seen in the bottom of the sketch.

In Sweden the prescription sales at pharmacies can for some species be assumed to cover the AMU almost entirely, e.g. for pigs, cats and dogs, where it is most common that the animal owners purchase and use antimicrobials based on a veterinary prescriptions. For other species or in other cases it can be more common that antimicrobials are first purchased by the veterinarian (requisition sales at the pharmacy) to be kept in store and used when needed at a farm or veterinary clinic. Figure 4 shows a conceptual sketch of different scenarios of AMU in Sweden.

The requisition sales do not contain information on when the medical products will be used, on what species, or at what geographical location, as that is not known at the moment of purchase. In these cases, it is important to have veterinary records describing the AMU. This requires good systems to collect and store these records, and to make sure they are of good quality. This has not

been the case historically in Sweden, which is one explanation to why there is no processes in place to estimate AMU. However, the new system to collect veterinary records on AMU will enable better estimations of AMU. This can lead to creation of workflows to continuously calculate and monitor AMU, but as mentioned, this will require more work, tests and validation with real data. In the longer term we hope that Sweden, as well as other countries that do not yet have workflows to calculate AMU, can process their data into the suggested common data structure, and use the tools developed later in WP2.

Figure 4 - Conceptual sketch of different scenarios of AMU in Sweden

CS2 - NEXT STEPS

Based on the common data structure we can then proceed with deliverable 2.3 and 2.4, to use the data (in our case simulated data according to the documentation of the common data structure) for analysis and to develop a dashboard, that aims to enhance AMU monitoring and improve decision making. In the future this data could also be combined with AMR data to make more advanced analyses on how AMU and AMR are connected. The analyses within the dashboard might consist of trends over time, comparison between species, regions etc.

Further on it will also be important to include information about animal population at risk or other similar information in the common data structure, to not only compare the actual amount of antimicrobials used but in relation to the animal population, which enables better comparisons. This can be done through various different indicators to measure AMU, and the different indicators could be used for different purposes. This will require even more data sources and extended workflows.

Figure 5 shows a sketch of the processes described in this deliverable, and development of tools for monitoring AMU based on the common data structure (conducted in later deliverables in WP2). The tool or tools for analysing and visualising AMU could for example be developed as an R-package (using the open-source programming language R) containing a dashboard built with the R-shiny framework, and published as open source to increase reusability.

Figure 5 – Conceptual diagram of workflows to process data into the suggested common data structure, and further steps where tools are developed to monitor AMU based on the common data structure.

Case study 3 – Economic security, transboundary spread of African Swine Fever

CS3 - BACKGROUND

Commercial pig movements are an important factor in the spread of African swine fever (ASF). The analysis of these movements can provide valuable intelligence for preparedness and outbreak response. For example, network analysis can determine a movement network's effectiveness at transmitting infection, and the relative importance of different holdings and connections therein. Additionally, incorporating detailed movement data into disease transmission models can improve the accuracy of predictions of these models, such as final outbreak size, and the speed at which this is reached. The effective use of pig movement data for these purposes is, however, complicated by a variety of challenges, including issues relating to data, and requirements for specific analytic expertise.

The aim of WP2 for CS3 is to address these challenges by developing a toolkit that facilitates the dataflow from pig movement data to network analysis and to transmission models of ASF, and that helps users with interpreting the outputs from these analyses. This toolkit comes in the form of an open-source R package, *movenet*⁹, and an accompanying interactive app¹⁰ to cater to users who prefer a graphical user interface. These tools are being developed through all tasks in WP2.

In this task we developed *movenet* functionalities to address data-related issues. As the main developer of *movenet* did not have direct access to any pig movement dataset, a FAIRification workflow was not considered feasible. Instead, we considered interoperability in a broader sense, and, given the topic of this case study, we focused on two data issues inhibiting international collaborative analysis of pig movement data: (1) the diversity of formats of movement and holding data employed in different countries; and (2) the commercial sensitivity of movement and holding data, resulting in difficulties sharing data.

To address the diversity of data formats, we considered that a first required functionality would be the flexible parsing of movement and holding data, and reformatting of these data to a common data structure that could function as input to any analytic workflows. The next section, “CS3 - Common data structure and content documentation and mapping”, describes this common data structure, and how its content maps to the various data structures in DigiVet countries. The subsequent section, “CS3 - Workflow to create common data structure”, describes the flexible-parsing-and-reformatting functionality we developed to facilitate the conversion to the common data structure.

To address the commercial sensitivity of movement and holding data, we developed a privacy-enhancing workflow, which is described in “CS3 - Privacy-enhancing workflow”.

CS3 - COMMON DATA STRUCTURE AND CONTENT DOCUMENTATION AND MAPPING

In devising a common data structure, we considered data requirements for network analysis and transmission modelling, as well as what types of holding and movement data are regularly collected in different DigiVet countries.

⁹ <https://digivet-consortium.github.io/movenet/>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/movenetapp>

Table 2 and Table 3 show the variables included in the common data structures for pig movement data and for holding data, respectively.

Table 2 - Common data structure, pig movement data

Column	Variable	Explanation	Required ?	Format required in <i>movenet</i> input data file (delimited text)	Format (R class) in common data structure
1	from	Identifier of origin holding	Required	Character	Character
2	to	Identifier of destination holding	Required	Character	Character
3	date	Date of the movement	Required	Date (any format) The applied date format specification must be specified in the config file.	Date
4	weight	Movement quantity or batch size (number of pigs moved)	Required	Numeric	Numeric
Any >4		Any other movement-related data	Optional		

Table 3 – Common data structure, holding data

Column	Variable	Explanation	Required?	Format required in <i>movenet</i> input data file (delimited text)	Format (R class) in common data structure
1	id	Unique identifier of holding (matching variables “from” and “to” in Table 2)	Required	Character	Character
Any >1	coordinates	Geographical coordinates of holding. The common data structure uses the ETRS89 reference system. Input files can use any coordinate reference system; this must be specified in the config file.	Optional	2 separate variables: coord_x: numeric coord_y: numeric	Simple feature geometry list-column (sfc, sfc_POINT)
Any >1	type	Type of holding or herd	Optional	Character	Character
Any >1	herd_size	Holding or herd size	Optional	Numeric	Numeric
Any >1		Any other holding or herd-related data	Optional		

Each common data structure focuses on one or more required variables, corresponding to minimal data requirements for basic temporal network analysis. These variables are placed in a defined order at the start of the data structure, so that they can be easily identified in *movenet*'s analytic workflows. Their formats are defined in R, using common standards to improve interoperability.

In addition to the required variables, each common data structure allows for the inclusion of user-defined optional variables, to use in more advanced analyses. These optional variables are located after the required variables, at the end of the data structure. For holding data, we defined several specific optional variables that are expected to be of particular value when analysing pig movement data; like the required variables, they have specific formatting requirements.

The defined variables in the common data structures are generally available in the countries participating in DigiVet, but with slightly different formats. In attachment “D2.2 - CS3 ASF - Content mapping and common data structure.xlsx” we show how variables from each country can be mapped to the common data structure. The attachment also contains metadata describing the datasets.

CS3 - WORKFLOW TO CREATE COMMON DATA STRUCTURE

Some processing is needed to convert original movement and holding data as stored by DigiVet countries to the common data structures described in the previous section. This can be done automatically with the *movenet* package.

To ensure correct reading of input data regardless of format, *movenet* requires users to supply one or more configuration (config) files, indicating how the package should read any incoming movement and holding data files. These config files must contain two groups of configurations: a set of file and data options that commonly vary between datasets, such as encoding (see Table 4 and Figure 6); and a mapping of common data structure variables to column headers (or indices) in the input file (see Figure 6).

Table 4 - *movenet* configurations: file and data options

Configuration	Required in which config file types?	Explanation
separator	Movement, holding	Separator (or delimiter) character used in the data file
encoding	Movement, holding	Encoding used in the data file
decimal	Movement, holding	Decimal mark used in the data file
date_format	Movement	Date format specification used in the data file
coord_EPSG_code	Holding – only required if coordinates are to be included within the common data structure	Numeric part of the EPSG code for the coordinate reference system used in the data file
country_code	Holding – only required if coordinates are to be included within the common data structure	Two-letter country code for the data in the data file

```

holdingdata_fileopts:
  separator: "," #Separator (delimiter) character used in holding datafile
  encoding: "UTF-8" #Encoding used in holding datafile
  decimal: "." #Decimal mark used in holding datafile
  coord_EPSG_code: 27700 #EPSG code for the Coordinate Reference System used (numeric part only)
  country_code: "UK"

holdingdata_cols:
  id: "cph" #Identifier of holding - need to match from/to in movement data
  coord_x: "easting" #Geographical coordinate (x/longitude) of holding (decimal, NOT degree/min/sec)
  coord_y: "northing" #Geographical coordinate (y/latitude) of holding (decimal, NOT degree/min/sec)
  type: "holding_type" #Type of holding or herd
  herd_size: "herd_size" #Size of herd

```

Figure 6 - Example holding config file with file and data options (*holdingdata_fileopts*) and data variable mapping (*holdingdata_cols*).

Example config files for some of the DigiVet countries’ data formats, as well as empty templates and instructions for users to create their own config files, are available in the *movenet* package¹¹.

¹¹ See also <https://digivet-consortium.github.io/movenet/articles/configurations.html> for a more detailed explanation.

Once an appropriate config file has been provided to *movenet*, a delimited movement or holding data file can be read in and converted to the appropriate common data structure. Format requirements for variables in the delimited input files are described in Table 2 and Table 3, along with the corresponding variables in common data structures. At this stage, *movenet* extracts the required variables and any optional variables indicated in the config file variable mapping, and re-orders the columns to match the common data structure. If coordinates are provided, these are transformed from the original coordinate reference system indicated in the config file to the ETRS89 reference system. Column headers are generally preserved from the input files, although they are made ASCII-compliant.

After conversion of movement and holding data to their respective common data structures, they can be merged with similarly formatted data from other countries (provided that holding identifiers are unique). The common data structures can also be plugged into the *movenet* privacy-enhancing workflow described below, and the *movenet* analytic workflows summarised in “CS3 – Next steps”.

CS3 - PRIVACY-ENHANCING WORKFLOW

The ability to share livestock movement data between different countries or organisations is of particular importance when modelling the spread of a transboundary disease threat like ASF. To address concerns around the commercial sensitivity of livestock movement data, and increase the potential for data sharing, we developed a privacy-enhancing workflow within *movenet*.

This privacy-enhancing workflow includes a range of functions that can be used to modify different aspects of movement and/or holding data, to make them altogether less identifiable.

Pseudonymisation

A function is provided that pseudonymises common data structure-format movement and/or holding data, by substituting holding identifiers with a randomly assigned integer and an optional prefix (e.g. “Farm1”) or by using a user-provided pseudonymisation key. The applied pseudonymisation key is provided as output, so that it can be saved for later re-identification of holdings.

Generation of synthetic data

At the time of writing, functions are provided that allow users to create synthetic movement data from common data structure-format movement data, by modifying dates, weights, and/or other numeric data fields. Each of these elements can be modified either by applying a uniformly distributed amount of noise, or by rounding.

Additionally, a function to create synthetic holding data is in development: this will allow users to substitute holding coordinates in a density-dependent manner, based on Voronoi tessellation. This functionality will be added to the open-access *movenet* GitHub repository in due course.

CS3 – STEPS BEYOND DELIVERABLE 2.2

Conversion of movement and holding data to common data structures is only the first step in any *movenet* workflow.

Development of the *movenet* R package for the effective use and analysis of pig movement data in African swine fever preparedness spans the various tasks of WP2.

In Task 2.3, we developed workflows for the integration of movement and holding data into disease transmission models, and for network analysis. The transmission modelling workflow links up with

the modelling package *SimInf*¹² (“A framework for data-driven stochastic disease spread simulations”), by converting movement data and/or holding coordinates into a transmission matrix that can serve as input to a custom pre-compiled holding-unit SEIR model¹³ of ASF. The network analysis workflow links up with the Statnet¹⁴ suite of packages to generate dynamic network representations of movement data and to determine a range of network metrics relevant to disease spread. This workflow produces a standardised, downloadable report, with tables and figures displaying basic network properties such as the number of active holdings and edges (overall and over time), static network analyses of periodic (monthly or yearly) snapshots, temporal analyses including ingoing and outgoing contact chains (reachability), and component analysis. Interpretive text is also provided, to support decision-making and to facilitate uptake by users with limited network analysis expertise.

We developed a *shiny* app with a graphical user interface to the *movenet* toolkit, to extend the reach of the toolkit to people who do not normally use R. Like the main toolkit, the app is available as open-source software downloadable from GitHub¹⁶. We chose this solution as privacy concerns inhibit the public display of movement data as on a dashboard, and even the uploading of these data to a restricted-access web app hosted on a remote server may be problematic.

The ensemble of workflows developed for CS3 are visualised in Figure 7.

Figure 7 - Conceptual diagram of the workflow developed for CS3 in WP2. The first step (developed in this task) is to process data into the suggested common data structures. Further steps (being developed in Task 2.3) and the graphical interface (being developed in Task 2.4) are also shown.

¹² <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/SimInf/index.html>

¹³ <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/siminf4movenet>

¹⁴ <https://statnet.org/packages/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/movenetapp>